

THE EFFECT OF MOISTURE ON THE COMPRESSION-COMPRESSION
FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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The compression-compression fatigue behavior of several multidirectional graphite/epoxy laminates ($[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$, $[0/\pm 30]_{3S}$, $[0/\pm \theta/0]_{2S}$, $\theta=30^\circ, 45^\circ$) has been investigated as a function of moisture content. While the room temperature compressive strength is only moderately affected by the presence of up to 2% moisture in the composite, the fatigue life for a given stress amplitude and the apparent fatigue limit are significantly lowered, particularly for the quasi-isotropic $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$ laminate. Fatigue damage accumulation has been studied through dynamic modulus measurements, load decay under constant displacement testing, changes in residual strength with cycling and x-ray radiographic monitoring of damage build-up. The relative fatigue resistance of the various laminates in the presence of moisture is expounded, so also, the responsible fatigue failure modes and mechanisms operative in the moisture conditioned specimens are discussed.